

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF RETAIL ENTERPRISES IN THE REGIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the transition of trade enterprises to the market concept of development has changed their target functions, and this is reflected in the system of economic indicators characterizing the economic process. This article analyzes the activities of retail enterprises, the factors of development of the retail system. Marketing research of retail organizations was conducted.

Introduction Retail trade In a market economy, the retail trade system is one of the most important sectors of the country's economy. Because it is of great importance in meeting the daily needs of the population, ensuring the free circulation of goods and services, as well as being the main link connecting production and consumption. The country's population growth, changing consumer culture, increased urbanization processes and the widespread introduction of new technologies create the need to further develop the retail trade system.

In our country, economists have conducted a number of scientific studies on the development of trade services. Among them, S.S. Gulyomov and B.R. Ruzmetov can be mentioned. In their scientific works, they comprehensively approached the issues of developing the national economy, increasing the economic potential of regions, and developing the service sector, including trade services.[1.2].

The works of F.B. Abdukarimov (2011) examine the main problems of the trade economy in our country, the economic profitability and economic efficiency of trading enterprises, and the improvement of market mechanisms in trade. [3]

W. Reinartz (2011) argues that the challenges faced by businesses in global and globalizing retail are mainly related to supply chain issues and arise between firms in other countries. Retailing needs that respond to the characteristics of specific national markets are crucial for the success of retail businesses. [4]

The scientific research of Makhmatkulov, G. O., Sayfullayev, S., & Bobomirzayev, A. 2024 indicates the issues of improving the econometric analysis of the main indicators of the development trend of trade services. [5]

Today, we can see the growing development of the trade culture in retail enterprises operating in the cities and district centers of our country.

- Availability of a wide and stable variety of goods on the shelves;
- Quality of service; Product quality and safety;

- Transparency of prices; Development of trade infrastructure;
- Introduction of innovations; High professionalism of sales staff, their courtesy and attention to customers; Consideration of customer needs.

The task of using modern marketing services and technologies for effective advertising of products manufactured by retail enterprises in the regions has been set. Today, many industrial enterprises of society are in the first place in the process of developing a practical media plan, taking into account their own needs for online advertising. If we pay attention to the growth rate of retail trade in our country, we can see significant changes. (Table 1).

Retail sales volume growth rate (annual)¹

Republic and regions	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Republic of Uzbekistan	105	109	113	113,8	114,5	115,5	116,7
Republic of Karakalpakstan	104,3	108,6	110,6	111,4	112,2	113,2	115,9
Andijan region	106,8	110,9	108,9	109,7	108,4	108,4	112,9
Bukhara region	104,9	111,5	115,5	108	106,2	106,2	110,9
Jizzakh region	109,9	111,1	115,1	109,7	107,6	107,6	107,4
Kashkadarya region	102,9	111,6	109,6	111,9	112,9	108,9	114
Navoi region	105,4	111,8	115,8	110,2	110,8	112,8	114,8
Namangan region	105,2	115,5	120,5	113,3	108,3	109,3	112,4
Samarkand region	106,4	107,3	108,3	109,5	111,9	112,9	115,2
Surkhandarya region	102,1	108,3	112,3	112	108,3	108,3	111,8
Syrdarya region	106,9	109,3	116,3	103,7	106,7	106,7	109,4
Tashkent region	97,1	100,6	118,6	109,8	110,9	110,9	114,6
Fergana region	106,2	108,6	118,6	105,6	112,3	112,3	115,9
Khorezm region	110,9	113,8	113,8	112,9	107,6	107,6	113,2
Tashkent city	103,6	112,6	120,6	111,8	114,5	114,5	114,9

The highest growth rate of retail trade turnover in the last 7 years (2018-2024) was observed in 2024. At the same time, retail trade turnover amounted to 111.7% compared to the same period in 2018.

Effective use of Internet marketing and other forms of trade in the regions of the republic is a requirement of the times. Trading via the Internet is currently a modern type of trade. Consumers can order and purchase the goods they need through their computers, tablets and mobile phones.

Realistic conditions will be created for business entities providing retail services to effectively use all resources involved in the sector, especially labor resources.

Despite the fact that at the initial stages of the introduction of trade through online services, the creation and application of new technologies is carried out at the expense of large expenditures, at the subsequent stages, income increases much faster than expenses. Because in online trade, unlike traditional trade, the law of diminishing returns on subsequent added value does not apply. The initial large expenditures associated with the creation of an electronic environment system in industrial enterprises are compensated by the expenses of

¹ O'rganishlar natijasida muallif ishlanmasi

subsequent stages. As a result, the profits of trading enterprises tend to increase. At the same time, the accumulation of excess reserves is prevented, and the shortage of goods is eliminated. In addition, the conditions for marketing in trading enterprises are significantly improved, and the costs associated with it are reduced.

Online shopping also provides a number of advantages for the population, reducing consumer spending, saving time on purchasing goods, significantly accelerating the process of finding goods, and creating the opportunity to contact stores at any time of the day and satisfy their needs.

The development of online shopping services creates the opportunity to create an ecosystem that provides comprehensive services. Ecosystems are an important component of the “green” economy, the foundation of sustainable development.

The following can be included as key drivers of digital transformation in the trade sector:

1. **Expansion of e-commerce platforms – increased opportunities for trading through online stores, marketplaces (for example, OLX, ZoodMall, Wildberries).**
2. **Mobile technologies and applications – use of convenient mobile applications and services for buyers (mobile banking, online payment systems, delivery services).**
3. **Digital payment systems – popularization of online payment services such as “Payme”, “Click”, “Apelsin”, expansion of cashless payments.**
4. **Automation of logistics and delivery systems – fast tracking of orders, digitalization of delivery services.**
5. **Artificial intelligence and data analytics – study of buyer behavior, improvement of marketing strategies, introduction of personalized services.**

The development of retail enterprises in the region is directly related to the stability of the domestic market, the socio-economic well-being of the population, and the improvement of the business environment. The study found that the following factors have a strong impact on the sustainable development of this sector:

Economic factors - real incomes of the population, the size of the consumer basket, the level of regional economic development and production indicators - directly affect the volume of retail trade. Along with income growth, the purchasing power of the population increases and trade networks expand.

Socio-demographic factors - the number of the population, demographic composition, the level of urbanization and changes in consumer culture determine the activity and development of the trade network. In particular, the increase in the number of young people is leading to the emergence of new consumer demands and service delivery methods.

Technological factors - the development of digital technologies, e-commerce platforms, mobile applications and payment systems is increasing the efficiency of retail trade and creating convenience for consumers. Also, the modernization of logistics services and automated management systems are accelerating trade processes.

The development of retail enterprises in the region is one of the important factors of the modern economy. Their effective operation not only ensures the provision of high-quality and convenient services to the population, but also has a significant impact on regional economic development. Factors influencing development include the development of market

infrastructure, changes in consumer demand, the level of use of modern information and communication technologies, the benefits and conditions created by the state, as well as the management capacity of the enterprise management.

List of used literature:

1. Гулямов С.С. и др. Системный анализ эффективности производства в рыночных условиях. – Т.: “Мехнат”, 1992
2. Рузметов Б.Р. Комплексное развитие региона в условиях углубления экономических реформ. Автореф. дисс. док. эк. наук. -Т.: 1998. - 39 с.
3. Abdukarimov F.B. (2011) Savdoda bozor mexanizmini takomillashtirish va samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari (Samarqand viloyati misolida). Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya. Samarqand: SamISI, 156 b.
4. Reinartz W. (2011) et al. Retailing innovations in a globalizing retail market environment // Journal of Retailing. –Т. 87. –С. S53-S66.
5. Maxmatqulov, G. O., Sayfullayev, S., & Bobomirzayev, A. (2024). Savdo xizmatlarining rivojlanish tendensiyasi asosiy ko'rsatkichlarining ekonometrik tahlili. Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil, 2(4), 139-149.

